

Can Chikung (Qigong) Enhance Oral Health and Well-being? A Review of the Evidence.

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Abstract: Background: Qigong, an ancient Chinese mind-body practice integrating movement, breath, and mental focus, offers diverse health benefits including stress reduction and improved well-being. Recognized in the West as a traditional vegetative biofeedback therapy, it has shown promise in enhancing quality of life, particularly for those with chronic conditions.

Objective: This review aimed to evaluate Qigong's potential benefits for dental professionals and patients, focusing on its impact on stress, posture, musculoskeletal pain, and overall well-being within the dental context.

Results: Qigong demonstrated significant reductions in stress, anxiety, and depression, positively influencing oral health. It also attenuated burnout, improved sleep, reduced fatigue, and enhanced well-being. Furthermore, it promoted postural improvements, musculoskeletal pain relief, and optimized biomechanics, suggesting potential for mitigating occupational injuries in dental professionals. Qigong emerges as a promising preventive intervention, enhancing both physical and psychological quality of life.

Conclusions: Qigong shows potential as a valuable therapeutic adjunct in dentistry, particularly for stress-related conditions and postural imbalances. It also offers a promising approach to addressing occupational hazards in dental professionals. However, due to limited direct research on Qigong within dentistry, further rigorous studies, including randomized controlled trials, are crucial to establish its specific effects on oral health outcomes and guide its clinical integration.

Keywords: Dentistry; Dental Medicine; Qigong; Traditional Chinese Medicine.

Citation: Abreu C., Couto R., Engler E.P., Viegas M., Nascimento C., Silva B. Can Chikung (Qigong) Enhance Oral Health and Well-being? A Review of the Evidence. *Journal of Complementary Therapies in Health*. 2025;3(1) 10.5281/zenodo.14946799

Academic Editor: Jorge Rodrigues

Received: 5 February 2025

Reviewed: 12 February 2025

Accepted: 28 February 2025

Published: 28 February 2025

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1. Introduction

Qigong is a Traditional Chinese Medicine discipline with its first archaeological records dating back to around 5000 BC ¹⁻³. Currently, in the West, it is seen as a traditional vegetative biofeedback therapy ⁴ where regular practice can produce psychophysiological changes ⁵. Automating these processes for everyday life results in constant improvement of physical and mental health, and prevention of illnesses ^{6,7}.

Commonly, Qigong is a collection of ancient practices that integrate controlled breathing, gentle physical postures and movements, and focused mental imagery to cultivate and balance vital energy within the body and mind ⁵. It has been shown to have a wide range of health benefits ⁸, including improved physical and mental well-being ^{7,9}. It can also be beneficial for patients with serious illnesses by enhancing their quality of life ^{8,10,11}.

Good oral health is essential for overall well-being ^{12,13}. It does not only contribute to a beautiful smile but also plays a crucial role in preventing various health issues ^{14,15}. As well, stress, anxiety and depression symptoms are often overlooked factors that can significantly affect oral health ¹⁶⁻¹⁸. These psychological factors can lead to detrimental oral

habits such as bruxism, clenching, and nail biting, which can cause significant damage to teeth and gums. Furthermore, stress can weaken the immune system, making individuals more susceptible to oral infections¹⁹⁻²¹.

This review aims to investigate the potential benefits of Qigong within the context of dental medicine. Specifically, the review will explore its possible impact on both dental professionals and patients.

2. Stress, pain and posture

Stress can be defined as the physiological or psychological response to internal or external pressures. It triggers a cascade of changes throughout the body, influencing how individuals feel and behave²².

By inducing mind-body changes, stress directly contributes to the development of psychological and physiological disorders, impacting both mental and physical health and ultimately reducing overall quality of life²².

Studies have demonstrated Qigong's efficacy in reducing stress levels across diverse populations. It has been shown to benefit not only the general population²³ but also individuals in high-stress occupations, such as computer operators²⁴. Furthermore, Qigong has been found to alleviate stress associated with specific health conditions, including hypertension²⁵ and chronic neck pain²⁶.

Furthermore, research suggests that certain types of prolonged work postures combined with mental stress can lead to sustained activation of low-threshold motor units in the neck and shoulder muscles, resulting in metabolic overload²⁷⁻²⁹. In oral health, alongside stress, posture is closely related to the development of bruxism³⁰, temporomandibular disorders³¹ and other occlusal problems³².

Qigong has been associated with postural improvements³³⁻³⁵, which may contribute to pain management. In fact, evidence suggests that the practice of Qigong can produce improvements regarding cervical pain^{26,36}. These benefits on pain and biomechanical function may still be observed at 6- and 12-months post-assessment³⁷.

In another study³⁸, a Qigong intervention has been shown to improve neck mobility, prevent reduced mobility of the temporomandibular and shoulder joint, and reduce sleep problems in surviving patients of nasopharyngeal cancer.

Also, a recent systematic review³⁹ suggests that Qigong may be a promising approach to improving joint mobility and alleviating trismus.

Through improvements in posture, pain and alleviation of stress, Qigong may be regarded as a promising beneficial therapeutic tool to improve biomechanical disturbances that are related to oral health.

3. Sleep, fatigue, anxiety and depression

Sleep, fatigue, anxiety, and depression are interconnected factors that significantly impact overall health and well-being⁴⁰. When sleep is disrupted, fatigue sets in, affecting energy levels, mood, and productivity⁴¹. Chronic fatigue can exacerbate anxiety and depression, leading to a vicious cycle. Anxiety and depression, in turn, can disrupt sleep patterns, further compounding the issue⁴².

The results of the study by Asawa *et al.*⁴³ suggest that disturbed sleep, fatigue, and a lack of vitality are interconnected and can significantly impact oral health. In agreement, the study by Rovas *et al.*⁴⁴ found that oral health behaviours tend to decline when individuals experience higher levels of stress, fatigue, and sleep disturbances.

Several studies have been conducted to understand the benefits of Qigong on sleep quality. The practice has been shown to have effects on psychological well-being, improving sleep duration⁴⁵ and the quality of sleep⁴⁶⁻⁴⁹ in the general population, but also under specific conditions such as in patients with chronic fatigue syndrome⁴⁹, radiotherapy treatment for prostate cancer⁵⁰, adults with cognitive impairment⁴⁶, Parkinson's disease⁴⁸, and in premenopausal women⁴⁷.

In addition to these benefits, Qigong also has positive effects in situations related to fatigue^{51,52}, anxiety^{53,54}, and depression^{49,55,56}, promoting a better quality of life⁵⁷. According to Rodrigues *et al.*⁵⁸, as a traditional mindfulness cognitive-behavioural therapy, Qigong may allow the users to learn new neuro-vegetative patterns that can model physically disturbed sensations (produced by psychological stress as an example), promoting the learning and modelling of new cognitive processes and patterns.

Through improvements in sleep, fatigue, anxiety, and depression levels, qigong is suggested to improve oral health behaviours. However, specific studies are needed to observe this relation.

4. For dental medicine professionals

Dental medicine professionals frequently encounter occupational challenges that can significantly impact their health and well-being. These challenges include prolonged static postures, repetitive movements, and exposure to ergonomic stressors, which can contribute to musculoskeletal disorders, chronic fatigue, and even burnout. These occupational hazards can have a detrimental impact on the physical and mental health of these professionals⁵⁹.

As previously discussed, Qigong demonstrates potential in addressing postural imbalances, as evidenced by studies showing improvements in posture³³⁻³⁵. This can translate, for example, to effective management of cervical and lumbar pain⁶⁰. Moreover, Qigong may serve as a preventive measure for work-related injuries by enhancing overall body biomechanics and flexibility³⁷.

Furthermore, considering the potential psychological impact of the dental profession, Qigong may offer valuable benefits in managing stress-related issues such as anxiety and depression^{49,53-56}. Notably, studies with other healthcare professionals have demonstrated Qigong's effectiveness in mitigating burnout symptoms^{61,62} and improving sleep quality⁶³.

A study by Malloy *et al.*⁶⁴ involving dental hygienists found that mind-body practices like Tai Chi and Qigong were among the most frequently utilized complementary therapies to address work-related musculoskeletal disorders. Importantly, this research concluded that the use of such therapies, including Qigong, positively impacted both physical and psychological quality of life.

5 - Discussion

This review explored the potential applications of Qigong in dental medicine, focusing on its impact on stress, posture, musculoskeletal pain, and overall well-being for both patients and dental professionals. The evidence suggests that Qigong offers promising benefits in several key areas relevant to dental health. As stress is a significant contributor to various oral pathologies, including temporomandibular dysfunction, orofacial pain, and bruxism^{65,66}, the stress-reducing effects of Qigong, demonstrated by reductions in ACTH and increases in β -endorphins⁶⁷, could be particularly valuable. Furthermore, the emphasis on breath control in Qigong practice may positively influence conditions linked to dysfunctional breathing patterns, such as dry mouth, dental cavities, periodontal disease, and even craniofacial development^{68,69}. These benefits extend to dental professionals, who often experience work-related stress and musculoskeletal issues. Qigong's potential to improve posture³³⁻³⁵ and alleviate musculoskeletal pain^{26,36} could be particularly beneficial in mitigating occupational hazards faced by dental professionals. The observed improvements in sleep quality⁴⁶⁻⁵⁰ and reductions in fatigue, anxiety, and depression^{49,51-56} further support the potential of Qigong to enhance overall well-being, which can indirectly influence oral health behaviors^{43,44}.

While the mechanisms underlying Qigong's effects are still under investigation, research suggests that mind-body exercises like Qigong can induce structural and functional changes in the brain, particularly in areas associated with cognitive control and emotional

regulation⁷⁰. This may explain the observed improvements in stress management, mood, and overall well-being.

Despite the promising findings, this review is limited by the scarcity of research specifically examining the application of Qigong in dental medicine. This gap in the literature makes it difficult to draw definitive conclusions about the specific effects of Qigong on oral health outcomes and its optimal implementation in dental settings. Furthermore, the quality of existing studies varies, with some exhibiting methodological limitations such as small sample sizes and lack of control groups. Future research, including well-designed randomized controlled trials with larger samples, is crucial to address these limitations and rigorously evaluate the efficacy and safety of Qigong in dental medicine. Investigating different Qigong styles and their specific effects on various aspects of oral health and occupational well-being in dental professionals would also be valuable.

6. Conclusions

The discussion presented in this review demonstrates that Qigong can be a valuable addition to dental practice. The benefits observed in previous studies, such as stress reduction, posture improvement, and pain relief, suggest that Qigong can be used to manage stress-related oral health issues and address occupational hazards faced by dental professionals. The evidence indicates potential benefits for stress reduction, posture improvement, pain management, and enhanced psychological well-being, all of which can positively impact oral health and professional performance. However, due to the limited availability of specific research in this area, further rigorous investigation, including randomized controlled trials, is necessary to fully elucidate the effects of Qigong in dental medicine and to develop evidence-based recommendations for its integration into clinical practice.

Author Contributions: Conceptualization, Conceptualization, C.A.; R.C. and E.P.E.; Methodology, C.A.; R.C. and E.P.E.; Validation, C.A.; Formal analysis, C.A.; R.C. and E.P.E.; Investigation, C.A.; R.C. and E.P.E.; Resources, C.A.; R.C. and E.P.E.; Writing - Original Draft, C.A.; R.C.; E.P.E.; M.V. and C.N.; Writing - Review & Editing, C.A.; R.C.; E.P.E.; M.V.; C.N. and B.S.; Visualization, C.A.; R.C.; E.P.E.; M.V. and C.N.; Project administration, C.A.; R.C. and E.P.E. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Conflict of Interest: The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interest.

Funding: This research received no external funding.

Institutional Review Board Statement: Not applicable.

Informed Consent Statement: Not applicable.

Data Availability Statement: The original contributions presented in this study are included in the article. Further inquiries can be directed to the corresponding author.

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